

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR QUANTITATIVE ESTIMATION OF AMLODIPINE IN SOLID DOSAGE FORM

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1. ABSTRACT

Amlodipine is an Anti-Hypertensive drug, which comes under the class of Calcium channel blocker derivatives. Calcium channel blockers are a group of medications that disrupt the movement of calcium through calcium channels. These drugs are used to lower blood pressure by lowering the movement of calcium into the cells of the blood vessels walls. It makes easier to pump the blood through the blood walls. As a result, the heart doesn't have to work as hard and blood pressure lowers. The developed ultraviolet spectrophotometric method was simple, sensitive, accurate, precise and economic for the development and validation of Amlodipine in bulk and tablet dosage form. In this present study, the analytical method validation and development of Amlodipine was done using the different parameters of method validation as per International Council for Harmonisation Q2(R1) guidelines. Rectified Spirit using as a solvent and it shows the maximum wavelength at

239 nm and then performed all the parameters of analytical method validation like accuracy, linearity, range limit of detection and limit of quantitation. Amlodipine showed linearity over the range of 03-30 µg/ml. The correlation coefficient value obtained was 0.9993 with the regression equation $y=0.033x + 0.007$ The accuracy studies was done in spiking method and the recoveries ranging from 99.39%-99.72%.The standard deviation was 0.001581 .The limit of detection was 0.529µg/ml and limit of quantitation was 1.603µg/ml respectively. The

method has shown good and consistent recoveries and is validated as per International Council for Harmonisation guidelines and can be used for routine quality control analysis of Amlodipine in dosage form.

2. INTRODUCTION

- Amlodipine is an angioselective calcium channel blocker and inhibits the movement of calcium ions into vascular smooth muscle cells and cardiac muscle cells which inhibits the contraction of cardiac muscle and vascular smooth muscle cells. Amlodipine inhibits calcium ion influx across cell membranes, with a greater effect on vascular smooth muscle cells. This causes vasodilation and a reduction in peripheral vascular resistance, thus lowering blood pressure. Its effects on cardiac muscle also prevent excessive constriction in the coronary arteries.
- Negative inotropic effects can be detected in vitro, but such effects have not been seen in intact animals at therapeutic doses. Among the two stereoisomers [R(+), S(-)], the (-) isomer has been reported to be more active than the (+) isomer.^[46] Serum calcium concentration is not affected by amlodipine. And it specifically inhibits the currents of L-type Cav1.3 channels in the zona glomerulosa of the adrenal gland.

Chemical Formula: C₂₀H₂₅ClN₂O₅

Weight Average: 408.876 gm

Therapeutic Categories

- Antihypertensive Agents Indicated for Hypertension
- Calcium Channel Blockers

- Dihydropyridines
- **Common side effects:** include swelling, feeling tired, abdominal pain, and nausea. Serious side effects may include low blood pressure or heart attack. Whether use is safe during pregnancy or breastfeeding is unclear. When used by people with liver problems, and in elderly individuals, doses should be reduced. Amlodipine works partly by vasodilation. It is a long-acting calcium channel blocker of the dihydropyridine type. Amlodipine was patented in 1982, and approved for medical use in 1990. It is on the World Health Organization's List of Essential Medicines. It is available as a generic medication.

3. PRINCIPLE OF UV-VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY

The Principle of UV-Visible Spectroscopy is based on the absorption of ultraviolet light or visible light by chemical compounds, which results in the production of distinct spectra. A UV-Vis spectrophotometer is an analytical instrument that measures the amount of ultraviolet (UV) and visible light that is absorbed by a sample. It is a widely used technique in chemistry, biochemistry, and other fields, to identify and quantify compounds in a variety of samples.

UV-Vis spectrophotometers work by passing a beam of light through the sample and measuring the amount of light that is absorbed at each wavelength. The amount of light absorbed is proportional to the concentration of the absorbing compound in the sample. Spectroscopy is based on the interaction between light and matter. When the matter absorbs the light, it undergoes excitation and de-excitation, resulting in the production of a spectrum. When matter absorbs ultraviolet radiation, the electrons present in it undergo excitation. This causes them to jump from a ground state (an energy state with a relatively small amount of energy associated with it) to an excited state (an energy state with a relatively large amount of energy associated with it). It is important to note that the difference in the energies of the ground state and the excited state of the electron is always equal to the amount of ultraviolet radiation or visible radiation absorbed by it. So the principle is based on the Beer's-Lambert's law. The Beer-Lambert Law (or Beer's Law) describes the linear relationship between the absorbance of light by a substance in solution and the concentration of the absorbing species. It is a foundational principle in spectrophotometry

Beer's law states that a beam of visible light passing through a chemical solution of fixed geometry experiences absorption proportional to the solute concentration. Beer's range of absorbance is **0.1-1.0**.

Advantages of using UV-visible spectroscopy in the validation of analytical methods:

1. Speed and Efficiency

Rapid Measurements: Provides quick results, allowing for high through put analysis.

2. Real-Time Monitoring

Enables real-time assessment of sample characteristics.

3. High Sensitivity

Can detect and quantify substances at very low concentrations, making it suitable for trace analysis.

4. Versatility

Broad Applicability: Suitable for a wide range of analytes, including organic and inorganic compounds.

Multiple Applications: Used for quantification, purity assessment, and stability studies.

5. Minimal Sample Preparation

Requires minimal preprocessing, saving time and resources.

Compatible with various sample types, including liquids and solutions

6. Non-Destructive Analysis

Preserves sample integrity in many cases, allowing for further testing or analysis

4. INSTRUMENTATION

□ Instrumentation and chemicals

Spectroscopy is the measurement and interpretation of electromagnetic radiation absorbed or emitted when the molecules or atoms or ions of a sample move from one energy state to another energy state. UV spectroscopy is a type of absorption spectroscopy in which light of the ultra-violet region (200-400 nm) is absorbed by the molecule which results in the excitation of the electrons from the ground state to a higher energy state.

The instrument employed in this research work is **UV Vis** spectrophotometer made by **Shimadzu (UV-1800i)**. For the **Amlodipine**. Quartz cells having 3 cm length with 1 cm path length were used for spectral measurement. On the basis of their solubility study, **Rectified Spirit** is selected as a solvent system.

Ultrasonicator (Model 5.5 150H) was used for sample solution preparation. Ultrasonication is one of the well-known highly practiced methods in stable nanofluids preparation. Ultrasonication is unique homogenization technique utilized in variety of applications. It is a process which break large particle into smaller fragment or better uniform sized particles in the base fluid.

5. MATERIAL AND METHODS

○ MATERIAL

1. Chemicals and Reagents

- Amlodipine standard (pure API).
- Suitable solvents (Rectified Spirit).

2. Instruments

- UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV 1800i)
- Quartz cuvettes (1 cm path length).
- Analytical balance.
- Ultrasonicator (optional for dissolving poorly soluble substances).

3. Glassware

- Volumetric flasks (10, 50, 100 mL).
- Pipettes and beakers.

○ METHODS

➤ Solubility Test

Solubility test of the drug amlodipine was performed by using various solvents. The solvents include water, Rectified Spirit, chloroform. But it was found that amlodipine soluble in Rectified Spirit.

➤ Determination of wavelength of maximum absorption (λ_{max})

A standard stock solution of Amlodipine was prepared using Ethanol as solvent. Then, the reference solution was scanned in the wavelength region of 200-400 nm.

➤ Preparation of standard stock solution

10g of Amlodipine was weighed out and transferred in a 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved with Rectified Spirit and made up the volume with the same. Then 1 ml was taken out from this solution and again diluted up to 10 ml with the same solvent to get 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution of Amlodipine standard.

➤ Preparation of standard sample solution

Average weight of 5 marketed Amlodipine tablets was taken and recorded. Weight equivalent to 10 mg of Amlodipine tablet was taken and mixed with water in a 100ml volumetric flask and made the volume up to the mark with the same solvent and filtered it. Then 1 ml of filtrate solution was taken out from this solution and diluted upto 10 ml with the same solvent in a 10 ml volumetric flask to get a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Both the solution was taken to UV-spectrophotometer for further

□ Preparation of calibration curve

The Calibration curve was prepared by using Stock to accomplish the seven-diverse calibration standard representing 3, 9, 15, 21, 27, 30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ strength. An absorbance of every calibration standard was estimated at λ_{max} 239 nm using fixed wavelength measurement mode. The calibration curves representing concentration vs. absorbance was plotted utilizing in Microsoft Excel 2010. Previously mentioned technique was rehashed multiple time with the goal that reproducible outcomes can be obtained.

➤ ASSAY

Ten tablets were accurately weighed and a quantity of tablet powder equivalent to 10mg of Amlodipine was weighed and then dissolved in 100ml of ethanol. The solution was the filled

and further diluted to obtained final concentration of 3, 9, 21 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. the sample solution was analysed and % of drug content was determined from the absorbance using the regression equation obtained in the calibration.

➤ **Recovery**

Three different solutions of Amlodipine were prepared in triplicate at level of 50%, 100% and 150% of its predefined concentration (15,20,25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). In predefined concentrations, different amount of Amlodipine was included (standard addition method) and accuracy was determined based on percent recovery.

6. METHOD VALIDATION PARAMETERS

□ **METHOD VALIDATION**

Developed UV method for the estimation of Amlodipine was validated in terms of parameters like linearity, range, accuracy, limit of quantification (LOQ) and limit of detection (LOD), Robbustness, Ruggedness, Inderday, Intraday using predefined calibration standards as portrayed below

• **LINEARITY AND RANGE**

➤ **Objective:** Assess the ability of the method to provide a proportional response to varying concentrations of Amlodipine.

➤ **Procedure**

Linearity of the proposed UV method was established using six different calibration standards. The absorbance of these solutions was observed against Ethanol as blank at 285 nm was observed and the obtained data was used for linearity calibration curve. Based on analysis of calibration standards, calibration curves in terms of absorbance vs. concentration plots were developed and R square value was considered to be important factor for establishing linearity of the proposed method. The interval between upper and lower concentration limit with acceptable linearity was reported to be the range of the proposed UV method.

➤ **Acceptance Criteria:** R^2 should be ≥ 0.999 , and residuals should be minimal.

• **ACCURACY**

➤ **Objective:** Evaluate the closeness of the measured values to the true value.

- **Procedure:** Accuracy of the developed method was carried out by performing recovery studies using standard addition method, in which standard drug was added in three different concentrations (50 %, 100 % and 150%) to the pre-analysed formulation (15,20,25µg/ml). The result of recovery studies is expressed in percentage Relative Standard Deviation (% RSD).

$$\%RC = (SPS - S / SP) \times 100$$

Where, % RC = Percent recovery

SPS = Amount found in the spiked sample

SP = Amount added to the sample

S = Amount found in the sample

- **Acceptance Criteria:** Recovery should be within 97–103%.
- **LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION (LOQ)**
 - **Objective:** Determine the smallest quantifiable amounts of Amlodipine.
 - **Procedure:** The LOQ was determined with the help of linearity curve, for the assay was calculated using the following formula.

In UV method development LOQ was determined by utilizing the following equation.

$$LOQ = 10 \times SD / S$$

Where, S= slope

SD= Standard deviation of Y-intercepts

- **Acceptance Criteria:** LOQ values should demonstrate method sensitivity. It may or may not be within the linearity range.
- **LIMIT OF DETECTION (LOD)**
 - **Objective:** Determine the smallest detectable amounts of Amlodipine.
 - **Procedure:** The LOD was determined with the help of linearity curve, for the assay was calculated using the following formula. In UV method development LOD was determined by utilizing the following equation

$$LOD = 3.3 \times SD / S$$

Where, SD= Standard deviation of Y-intercepts

S= Slope

➤ **Acceptance Criteria:** LOD values should demonstrate method sensitivity. It must be less than linearity range.

• **ESTIMATION OF AMLODIPINE CONTENT IN MARKETED FORMULATION**

➤ **Objective:** To determine the percentage of amlodipine in the marketed tablet.

➤ **Procedure**

Developed & prevalidated UV-Vis method was successfully used for estimation of Amlodipine content in marketed formulation. For the study, amlodipine Tablets were purchased and contents of Tablet were collected and suitable dilution were made using pre-optimized co-solvent system. Prepared samples were analyzed using pre validated UV-method & results were reported in terms of average percent assay.

➤ **Acceptance criteria:** Tablet should contain at least 90%-110%.

• **ROBUSTNESS**

➤ **Objective:** to ensure an analytical method's consistency when small, deliberate variations in method parameters are done.

➤ **Procedure:** The Robustness of the system is determined by measuring the absorbance of same sample having same concentration by different analyst under the same experimental conditions.

• **RUGGEDENESS**

➤ **Objective:** To ensure the method's performance remains stable and reliable when used routinely or transferred between different laboratories.

➤ **Procedure:** The Robustness of the system is determined by measuring the absorbance of same sample having same concentration by different UV spectrophotometer under the different laboratory conditions.

• **PRECISION**

➤ **Objective:** to ensure the reliability and consistency of measurement results by quantifying the degree of agreement among multiple measurements of the same sample under identical conditions

- **Procedure:** The Robustness of the system is determined by measuring the absorbance of same sample having same concentration multiple times.

- **SANDELL'S SENSITIVITY**

- **Objective:** Sandell sensitivity is a measure of how sensitive a spectrophotometric method is.
- **Procedure:** In UV method development Sandell sensitivity was determined by utilizing the following equation

$$=0.001*d/Slope(ug/ml)$$

- **MOLAR ABSORPTIVITY (ϵ)**

- **Objective:** molar absorptivity (ϵ), also known as the molar extinction coefficient, is a quantitative measure of how strongly a chemical species absorbs light at a specific wavelength.
- **Procedure:** In UV method development molar absorptivity was determined by utilizing the following equation

$$\epsilon = \text{Absorptivity(slope in mol/lit)}/\text{molecular mass}$$

7. OBSERVATION TABLE

- **Table 1: Calibration Curve Data.**

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
3	0.098
9	0.303
15	0.519
21	0.702
27	0.898
30	0.99

- **Table 2: Assay Data.**

conc ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	Actual concentration	%content	Mean
10	0.156	9.86	98.6	
20	0.259	19.58	97.92	97.95
30	0.361	29.20	97.33	

➤ **Table 3: Recovery Data.**

1) **Amlkind 10mg**

Level of Cons recovery %) volume (ml)	Added volume (ml)	Total volume (ml)	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	% Recovery	% mean recovery
50	1	0.5	15	0.508	102.62	
100	1	1	20	0.481	94.35	99.71
150	1	1.5	25	0.650	102.18	

2) **Amlip 10mg**

Level of recovery	Constant volume (ml)	Added volume (ml)	Total volume (ml)	Conc ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	% Recovery	% mean recovery
50	1	0.5	1.5	15	0.518	104.64	
100	1	1	2	20	0.650	97.42	99.39
150	1	1.5	2.5	25	0.800	96.12	

➤ **Table 4: Robustness.**

Sr. No.	Absorbance (9 μg)	% conc	Absorbance (15 μg)	% conc	Absorbance (21 μg)	% conc
Analyst 1	0.335	110.33	0.519	103.30	0.729	104.09
Analyst 2	0.337	111.11	0.509	101.41	0.721	103.00
Analyst 3	0.340	112.11	0.519	103.40	0.716	102.30
Analyst 4	0.345	113.77	0.506	100.80	0.702	100.28
Average		111.83		102.22		102.41
STDEV		1.48		1.32		1.60
RSD		1.32		1.29		1.56

➤ **Table 5: Ruggedness.**

concentration	Absorbance (1800i) 02887	% concentration	Absorbance (1800i) 02883	% concentration	average	STDEV	RSD
9μg	0.335	110.33	0.343	113.13	111.73	1.97	1.76
15 μg	0.519	103.30	0.530	105.65	108.80	1.66	1.52
21 μg	0.729	104.09	0.735	105.62	104.09	1.08	1.03

➤ **Table 6: LOD & LOQ**

Sr. No	Absorbance	Detected concentration(X)	Sigma(σ) (SD)	LOD 3.3* σ/m	LOQ 10* σ/m
1	-0.004	-0.2161	0.005294	0.5294	1.6
2	0.009	-0.2031			
3	-0.004	-0.2161			
4	0	-0.2121			
5	-0.002	-0.2141			
6	-0.005	-0.2171			
7	-0.002	-0.2141			
8	-0.004	-0.2161			
9	-0.011	-0.2231			

➤ Table 7: Intraday

Time	Absorbance (9µg)	% conc	Absorbance (15µg)	% conc	Absorbance (21µg)	% conc
12PM	0.325	107.07	0.509	101.41	0.722	104.18
3PM	0.311	104.71	0.515	102.62	0.715	102.16
5PM	0.319	105.05	0.520	103.63	0.730	104.32
Average		105.61		102.55		103.55
STDEV		1.27		1.11		1.20
RSD		1.20		1.08		1.15

➤ Table 8: Interday

Day	Absorbance (9µg)	% conc	Absorbance (15µg)	% conc	Absorbance (21µg)	% conc
Monday	0.312	102.22	0.516	102.80	0.704	100.57
Tuesday	0.320	104.44	0.528	105.20	0.714	102.00
Average		103.33		104.00		101.28
STDEV		1.57		1.69		1.01
RSD		1.52		1.63		0.99

➤ Table 9: Precision

1) Pure drug (Amlodipine Besylate)

Sr. No	Absorbance (9µg)	%conc	Absorbance (15µg)	% conc
1	0.324	106.66	0.523	104.20
2	0.326	107.33	0.520	103.60
3	0.324	106.66	0.522	104.00
4	0.325	107.00	0.523	104.20
5	0.327	107.66	0.527	105.00
6	0.322	106.00	0.520	103.60
Average		106.91		104.00
STDEV		0.319		0.282
RSD		1.32		1.29

2) Amlip 10mg

Sr. No.	Absorbance (9µg)	% conc	Absorbance (15µg)	% conc
1	0.324	106.66	0.523	104.20
2	0.326	107.33	0.520	103.60
3	0.324	106.66	0.522	104.00
4	0.325	107.00	0.523	104.20
5	0.327	107.66	0.527	105.00
6	0.322	106.00	0.520	103.60
Average		106.91		104.00
STDEV		0.319		0.282
RSD		1.32		1.29

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ Method development and optimization

Identification of wavelength of maximum absorbance is prerequisite for quantitative UV analysis. Solution representing absorbance value ranging from **0.1 – 1.0** is generally considered to be suitable for the determination of wavelength of maximum absorbance. Considering the prerequisite and the suitability, determination of maximum wavelength for Amlodipine solution (100 µg/mL) was carried out using full scan mode of UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Full scan was processed using UV software and the λ_{max} was identified. It was found to be **239 nm** for Amlodipine.

➤ Preparation of calibration curve

Quantification of unknown samples by UV-Visible spectrophotometer or any other instrumental method of analysis needs a reproducible calibration curve and an equation stating correlation between concentration and the response. As compare to graphical method, above stated method is widely accepted and reproducible in nature. Considering the utility of quantitative analysis of Amlodipine, calibration curve for Amlodipine was developed using seven different calibration standards. The absorbance of different calibration standards at 239 nm was recorded using fixed wavelength mode of UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Calibration curve was repeated three times and reported as shown in Table 1.

Figure 1: Calibration Curve for Amlodipine.

• Method Validation

□ LINEARITY AND RANGE

Proposed method is to be used for its optimum performance. Considering the importance of linearity and the range, seven point calibration curve of Amlodipine covering a range of **03-30 µg/ml** was developed. Details of concentrations and the respective mean absorbance values are depicted in Table 1. Calibration curve when subjected to least square regression analysis yielded an equation; $y = 0.033x + 0.0073$ with correlation coefficient **0.9993** as shown in Figure 1. From the linearity study, it was revealed that, developed UV method was linear in the pre-defined concentration range of calibration standards.

□ ACCURACY

Accuracy is a measure of the closeness of the experimental value to the actual amount of the substance in the matrix. Accuracy is to be established over the entire calibration range of the analytical method so that at any point of determination, results obtained would be reliable. In case of UV method for Amlodipine, accuracy was established using recovery studies. At **50 %** standard addition, mean recovery of Amlodipine was found to be **104.64%** whereas at **100** and **150 %** standard addition, it was found to be **97.42%** and **96.12%** respectively. **1.22% RSD** was found to be less than 2 for the Amlodipine recovery studies. From the results of accuracy studies, it was observed that developed UV method is highly accurate as the percent recovery was in between **99.39 to 99.71%** and the % RSD was well below 2%.

□ LIMIT OF QUANTITATION (LOQ) AND LIMIT OF DETECTION (LOD)

LOQ represents the lowermost concentration that can be analyzed with acceptable accuracy and precision. Generally, LOQ is the first calibration standard. **LOD** and **LOQ** of proposed

UV method was found to be **0.529 µg/ml** and **1.603 µg/ml** respectively. Lower LOQ value indicated that proposed method would be suitable for analyzing the samples containing even small quantities of Amlodipine.

□ **RUGGEDNESS:**

It represents that the method's performance remains stable and reliable when used routinely or transferred between different laboratories. The RSD of Ruggedness was found to be 1.03% which was well below 2%. From the results of studies, it was observed that developed UV method is highly accurate.

□ **ROBUSTNESS**

It represents that the method's performance remains stable and reliable when used routinely or transferred between different laboratories. The RSD of Robustness was found to be 1.56% which was well below 2%. From the results of studies, it was observed that developed UV method is highly accurate.

□ **INTERDAY**

It Interday precision (also called intermediate precision) refers to the degree of agreement between results of the same sample analyzed on different days (usually by the same analyst, using the same instrument and laboratory conditions). It measures the reproducibility of the method over time to ensure that results remain reliable when the method is applied on different days. The RSD of Interday was found to be 1.52% which was well below 2%. From the results of studies, it was observed that developed UV method is highly accurate.

□ **INTARDAY**

Intraday precision (also called repeatability) refers to the degree of agreement between results of replicate measurements of the same sample within the same day, usually performed by the same analyst under the same conditions. It shows how precise the method is when repeated several times in a single day. The RSD of Intraday was found to be 1.20% which was well below 2%. From the results of studies, it was observed that developed UV method is highly accurate.

Parameter	Results
Absorption maxima (nm)	239nm
Linearity range (µg/ml)	03-30 (µg/ml)
Standard regression eq. (y)	y=0.033x + 0.0075

Correlation coefficient (R ²)	0.9993
Accuracy (%recovery)	99.39 %(AMLOKIND 10MG) 99.71% (AMLIP 10MG)
Slope (m)	0.033
Y-intercept (c)	0.0075
Relative Standard Deviation	<2%
LOD (µg/ml)	0.529(µg/ml)
LOQ(µg/ml)	1.603(µg/ml)
Molar Absorptivity	14067.22 mol/lit
Sandell's Sensitivity	0.0303
Interday	1.52% (RSD)
Intraday	1.20 %(RSD)

9. CONCLUSION

A simple, accurate and precise UV-Visible spectrophotometric method for the estimation of Amlodipine was developed and validated. The method was developed using Rectified Spirit as solvent and the λ_{max} was found to be 239 nm. The method was validated with respect to linearity, precision, accuracy, sensitivity. The bulk and dosage forms were validated in terms of Accuracy, Linearity, Specificity, LOD, LOQ, Robustness, Ruggedness, Interday, Intraday, and Assay.

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